

PECULIARITIES OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS AFTER MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Relevance. Recently, in local and foreign literature, there has been an increased interest in assessing the quality of life (QOL) of patients with diseases of the cardiovascular system, since the traditional criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of various treatment methods no longer satisfy researchers and practitioners.

Purpose of the study. Assess the quality of life of patients with myocardial infarction.

Materials and methods of research: the study is based on the data of examination of 30 patients who had myocardial infarction at the age of 36 to 65 years. All patients included in this study were interviewed before and after treatment using the Minnesota Living with Heart Failure Questionnaire (MLHFQ).

Results of the study: The results of the study of the quality of life of patients indicate the presence of a number of general patterns, as well as group characteristics. The index of QOL before treatment in the group of patients who received a rehabilitation course of exercise therapy was 55.8 ± 5.7 versus 59.2 ± 5.8 in the comparison group ($P < 0.05$). When studying QOL in the dynamics of total indicators, QOL significantly differed in groups with rehabilitation effects of exercise therapy from the control group, the total indicator in the main group was 37.9 ± 3.8 points (against 55.8 ± 5.7 before rehabilitation), which is 1.5 times was lower than the initial level ($P < 0.05$). On the contrary, in the comparison group, no pronounced dynamics of the total QOL was observed. At the same time, patients of this group noted attacks of retrosternal pain; the need to limit their physical efforts; the need to constantly be treated, take medications, periodically lie in the hospital; additional material costs associated with the treatment of the disease.

In both groups of patients who received rehabilitation treatment, the results after a month on all questions of the questionnaire decreased, which characterized the positive effect of the rehabilitation impact. In the comparison group, non-significant deviations (decrease) were observed only in relation to 6, 6, 9, 17 and 19 questions of the MLHFQ. While in the group of patients who received exercise therapy, such insignificant decreases in indicators were observed in relation to 6, 17, 18 and 20 questions.

Conclusion. When analyzing the quality of life in patients with myocardial infarction, a sharp decrease in the total indicator and its effect on the indicators of the patient's functional abilities and vital activity were found. Under the influence of the inclusion of exercise therapy

in the complex of rehabilitation measures in patients who have had a myocardial infarction, the perception of the general state of health improves and life satisfaction increases.